

Local Government in Canada

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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1. The System of Local Government in Canada: An Introduction

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Types of Local Governments

Canadian federalism divides governing responsibilities among three levels of government: federal, provincial, and local. However, the Canadian Constitution gives the provinces sole jurisdiction over municipalities, which results in significant inter-provincial variation among local government systems. While the federal government in recent years began to provide money through joint federal-provincial programs for services that are ultimately delivered by municipalities (primarily hard infrastructure), there is typically no direct federal policy or regulatory involvement with the municipal level of government.² One side effect of this lack of federal involvement is that it is difficult to determine how many local governments there actually are in Canada. A comprehensive survey of available data from numerous sources, conducted in June 2021 by researchers at Western University,³ indicates that there were 3,533 local governments in Canada as of 2020. This is a significant decrease from the total of 4,432 in 1995, which reflects the results of a large-scale wave of provincial imposed consolidations in several provinces around the turn of the millennium. Despite this consolidation, most municipalities in Canada are small and rural. A report based on the 2016 census finds that only 723 had a population of 5,000 or greater. By contrast, 24 municipalities had over 200,000 residents, while three municipalities (Toronto, Montreal and Calgary) had over 1 million inhabitants. Toronto is Canada's largest municipality, with a population of 2.9 million as of July

¹ Acknowledgements: Data regarding number of municipalities in Canada, as well as the analysis of rural-urban demographic and economic differences in Ontario, were compiled and produced by Amanda Gutzke at Western University. Our sincere thanks for her excellent work.

² Erin Tolley and William R Young, 'Municipalities, the Constitution, and the Canadian Federal System' (Government of Canada 2001) <<http://publications.gc.ca/Collection-R/LoPBdP/BP/bp276-e.htm#Municipalities>> accessed 25 July 2019.

³ These data were collected and analyzed as part of another research project, led by Zack Taylor and Martin Horak.

2018.⁴ Just as the country’s 10 provinces and three territories⁵ vary in population size, so too do their municipal populations. Ontario tends to have larger municipalities as a result of its history of amalgamations imposed by the province, many of which took place in the 1990s.⁶ Ontario currently has 444 municipalities.

In some cases, urban municipalities have distinct status under provincial law. For example, Vancouver, Winnipeg, Montreal, and Saint John are Charter Cities, which means that they are governed by their own piece of legislation – or ‘Charter’ – rather than being subject to the broad, province-wide legislation that governs the activity of other municipalities.⁷ The City of Toronto is likewise governed by stand-alone provincial legislation. However, in general the degree to which these charters grant powers and resources over and above those of other municipalities is limited.

Table 1: Types of municipalities in Canada’s four most populous provinces.⁸

Province	Types of Municipality
Ontario	Village
	Township
	Town
	Municipality
	City
	County
	Regional Municipality
Quebec	Village
	Township
	United Township
	Town
	Municipality

⁴ ‘Municipalities in Canada with the Largest and Fastest Growing Populations between 2011 and 2016’ (*Statistics Canada*, 8 February 2017) <<https://www12.statcan.gc.ca/census-recensement/2016/as-sa/98-200-x/2016001/98-200-x2016001-eng.cfm>> accessed 1 August 2019; ‘Municipalities in Canada with Population Decreases between 2011 and 2016’ (*Statistics Canada*, 8 February 2017) <<https://www12.statcan.gc.ca/census-recensement/2016/as-sa/98-200-x/2016002/98-200-x2016002-eng.cfm>> accessed 1 August 2019; ‘Toronto at a Glance’ (*City of Toronto*, undated) <<https://www.toronto.ca/city-government/data-research-maps/toronto-at-a-glance/>> accessed 1 August 2019.

⁵ Canada’s three territories (Nunavut, the Northwest Territories, and Yukon) are located in the far north. Despite their large geographical size, they have very small populations, totaling only about 110,000 in all three territories, which is less than the population of the smallest province (Prince Edward Island, 150,000 inhabitants).

⁶ Andrew Sancton, *Canadian Local Government: An Urban Perspective* (2nd edn, OUP 2015) 150, 152.

⁷ ‘Power of Canadian Cities- The Legal Framework’ (*City of Toronto*) <https://www.toronto.ca/ext/digital_comm/inquiry/inquiry_site/cd/gg/add_pdf/77/Governance/Electronic_Documents/Other_CDN_Jurisdictions/Powers_of_Canadian_Cities.pdf> accessed 25 July 2019; John Stefaniuk, ‘Municipal Powers and their Limits’ (TDS Law) <<https://www.tdslaw.com/site-content/uploads/municipal-powers-and-their-limits-2.pdf>> accessed 25 July 2019.

⁸ Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 7-8; ‘Types of Municipalities in Alberta’ (*Government of Alberta*, undated) <<https://www.alberta.ca/types-of-municipalities-in-alberta.aspx>> accessed 25 July 2019.

	City Parish Regional Government Metropolitan Community Regional County Municipality
British Columbia	Village Town District Municipality City
Alberta	Summer Village Village Town City Specialized Municipality Municipal District Improvement District Metis Settlement Special Areas

Generally, Canadian municipalities are responsible for providing physical services including water supply, waste management, local infrastructure management, sewage treatment, planning and development services, libraries, parks and recreation, local police, and parking.⁹ These local government tasks are administered through general purpose municipalities (variously called cities, towns, villages, etc., depending on size), sometimes in conjunction with special purpose bodies. The table above compares the largest four provinces by population to illustrate variation in the legal types of municipalities. In addition to these, there are numerous local government bodies that do not have municipal status – such as British Columbia’s regional districts, which are multi-purpose service federations of municipal governments.

In some provinces, including Ontario, Quebec and Alberta, there is a single tier of local government in some areas, and two tiers of local government in other areas. Upper-tier governments in Ontario, for example, are either called counties or regional municipalities, with the latter typically found in large urban areas. Upper-tier municipalities are comprised of the lower-tier governments within their boundaries. They provide region-wide services like arterial roads; transit; policing; sewer and water systems; waste disposal; region-wide land use planning and development; and health and social services.¹⁰

⁹ ‘The Three Levels of Government’ (*Parliament of Canada*, undated) <https://lop.parl.ca/about/parliament/education/ourcountryourparliament/html_booklet/three-levels-government-e.html> accessed 25 July 2019.

¹⁰ ‘Ontario Municipalities’ (*AMO*, undated) <<https://www.amo.on.ca/AMO-Content/Municipal-101/Ontario-Municipalities.aspx>> accessed 25 July 2019.

Legal Status of Local Governments

Canada's Constitution specifies the terms of Canadian federalism. It assigns responsibility for local governments to the provinces. This means that the provincial governments have full jurisdiction over the local governments in their territory. Section 92 of the Constitution Act of 1867 specifies the powers of the provinces and Section 92(8) gives each provincial legislature the power to make laws for the municipal institutions under its jurisdiction. Municipalities are often referred to as 'creatures of the province' because they rely on the provinces for their legal existence.¹¹

There is significant variation among the provinces in terms of the structure of municipal legislation. Historically, provincial legislation has tended to lay out every power granted to its municipalities; if a specific power is not listed, municipalities do not possess that power. However, in recent years this has shifted, and most provinces now have legislation, such as that implemented in Alberta in 1995 and Ontario in 2001, which grants municipalities the same powers as a 'natural person' unless specifically excluded by the legislation. This gives municipalities the same rights as businesses to enter into contracts, own property, and make investments. Moreover, British Columbia's provincial government sets only broad legislation within which municipalities have the authority and flexibility to respond to each community's unique and changing needs. The Government of British Columbia views municipalities as autonomous and accountable to their democratically elected municipal councils.¹²

Both urban and rural municipalities in all Canadian provinces have some legal authority to act in the following functions: fire protection; animal control; roads; traffic control; solid waste collection and disposal (except in Prince Edward Island); land use planning and regulation; building regulation; economic development; tourism promotion; public libraries parks and recreation; cultural facilities; licensing of businesses; emergency planning and preparedness; rural fences and drainage; regulation and/or provision of cemeteries; airports (excluding major airports formerly operated by the federal government); and weed control and regulation of cosmetic pesticides.

Additionally, the following functions are typically delivered by urban municipalities: public transit; regulation of taxis; water purification and distribution; sewage collection and treatment; downtown revitalization; and regulation of noise. Generally, urban municipalities are also responsible for policing, although in some provinces special purpose bodies take care

¹¹ Tolley and Young, 'Municipalities and the Constitution', above; Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 27.

¹² For a comprehensive overview of Canadian municipal legislation, see Zack Taylor and Alec Dobson, 'Power and Purpose: Canadian Municipal Law in Transition' (2020) 47 IMFG Papers on Municipal Finance and Governance; 'Municipalities in British Columbia' (*British Columbia*, 2019) <<https://www2.gov.bc.ca/gov/content/governments/local-governments/facts-framework/systems/municipalities>> accessed 25 July 2019.

of this function. The exception is Newfoundland and Labrador, where policing is taken care of by the Royal Newfoundland Constabulary. Moreover, the Royal Canadian Mounted Police (RCMP) (or a provincial police force, as in the case in Quebec and Ontario) enters into contracts with some urban municipalities to provide policing, and it is typical for the RCMP or provincial police to provide policing in rural areas.

Ontario is unique in that the province mandates that its municipalities deliver certain social services. This includes income and employment assistance through the Ontario Works program and subsidized childcare with provincial oversight and financial assistance. Additionally, Ontario municipalities are required to provide subsidized social housing, with limited financial assistance from the province. Municipalities in other parts of the country do not have the same statutory responsibility to provide these social services.¹³

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

The fact that the provinces have under the Canadian Constitution sole jurisdiction over municipalities gives rise to considerable inter-provincial variation. Although municipal powers and responsibilities thus vary by province, common core functions include planning, regulating, protecting, and providing infrastructure services for the built environment.¹⁴

In some cases, there is also asymmetry within provinces in terms of how local government is structured, as different laws may exist for urban and rural municipalities. As noted above, several of Canada's largest urban municipalities are governed by charters that outline specific institutional arrangements for that municipality, and/or grant it additional powers and revenue sources. Toronto, for example, was granted charter status in 2007, giving it additional revenue raising tools beyond the property taxes and provincial transfers that most municipalities rely on. However, it should be noted that Charter Cities do not have additional constitutional protections. A municipal charter can be changed by the province at any time. Indeed, there is much disagreement surrounding the utility of granting cities such additional powers, as such powers have typically been limited and are often not fully used.¹⁵

General municipal statutes and special charters are not the only laws that apply to municipalities. Indeed, since provincial governments set parameters for municipal action in a multitude of policy fields, ranging from planning and environmental services to policing and housing, the scope of municipal action is shaped by dozens, if not hundreds of different statutes

¹³ Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 22-23.

¹⁴ Taylor and Dobson, 'Power and Purpose: Canadian Municipal Law in Transition', above.

¹⁵ Harry Kitchen, 'Is Charter City Status a Solution for Financing City Services in Canada – Or is that a Myth?' (University of Calgary School of Public Policy SPP Research Paper 9-2, 2016) <https://www.policyschool.ca/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/charter-city-status-kitchen_0.pdf> accessed 26 July 2019.

in each province.¹⁶ In addition, in some provinces, provincial governments may enact laws that apply only to particular municipalities or groups of municipalities – that is, single municipalities can apply to their provincial government to request private statutes as a remedy for a particular local problem for there is no other legal recourse.¹⁷

Political and Social Context in Canada

All Canadian municipalities are governed by a democratically elected council.¹⁸ Ward systems are commonly used, especially in large municipalities; Vancouver is Canada’s only large city where councillors are elected at-large. With the exception of the City of Vancouver and larger municipalities in the Province of Quebec, local government is non-partisan. The provinces of British Columbia and Quebec are the only two provinces that have legislation that allows for the existence of political parties at the local level.¹⁹ The fact that local government tends to be non-partisan, and that provincial party systems also tend to be quite distinct from the federal party system, means that the broader political context within which municipalities operate is marked by only weak political links among levels of government. This lack of vertical political integration, together with the weak legal status of local governments, made them the target of politically expedient decentralization in the fiscally lean 1990s. At that time, structural fiscal pressure on the welfare state produced a cascading decentralization of policy and fiscal responsibility through the Canadian federation, and municipalities had to cope with the imposition of unfunded or partly funded policy mandates from the provincial level. The result was intergovernmentally induced fiscal stress at the local level, which has only in recent years begun to be mitigated by increasing fiscal transfers.

Many scholars suggest that local governments, with their weak legal status, are primarily ‘policy takers’, rather than ‘policy-makers’, in the Canadian context.²⁰ There are certainly cases where Canadian municipalities do make policy independently of the provinces. To a significant extent, their ability to do so depends on their population size and their local property tax base. Since rural municipalities have both a small population and a weak property tax base, their autonomous policy-making capacity tends to be very limited. For both reasons, there is thus a policy capacity divide among Canadian municipalities that closely mirrors the rural/urban divide.

¹⁶ *ibid* 8.

¹⁷ Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 31.

¹⁸ However, upper-tier governments in two-tier systems (e.g., Greater Vancouver and Ontario’s regional municipalities) sometimes have indirectly elected councils composed of representatives of lower-tier municipalities.

¹⁹ Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 173, 180, 186, 188.

²⁰ *ibid* 251.

Like many post-industrial countries, Canada is highly urbanized. Almost 72 per cent of the population lives in urban areas with over 100,000 people, and more than a third of all Canadians live in the three largest urban areas (Toronto, Montreal and Vancouver).²¹ The Canadian population is thus concentrated primarily in a handful of large urban areas, whose population is growing quickly. By contrast, the population of rural Canada is (in most regions) growing much more slowly,²² and rural areas are on average older, whiter and poorer.

Table 2: Selected Demographic and Economic Indicators in Ontario, by Type of Census Division.²³

	Metropolitan	Mixed	Non-Metropolitan
Population change (2011-2016)	+ 5.57%	+ 4.54%	+ 0.92%
Visible minority population (2016)	43.5%	13.5%	2.6%
Average household income (2016)	\$78,477	\$73,258	\$65,748

An analysis of 2016 census data conducted for this report paints a picture of the demographic and economic contrasts between rural and urban areas in Ontario, Canada’s largest province by population (table above). The data are divided into three kinds of census divisions (CDs) – metropolitan CDs, which are located in urban areas with more than 100,000 people; non-metropolitan CDs, which are fully outside settlements with more than 100,000 people; and mixed CDs, which include a combination metro and non-metro areas. As is clear from the table, non-metropolitan – that is, rural and smaller-town – CDs grew much more slowly in population than others between 2011 and 2016; they were also much whiter, with only 2.6 per cent of the population identifying as visible minority, as opposed to 43.5 per cent in metropolitan CDs; and they were poorer, with an average household income that was only 83.7 per cent of the metropolitan average. These demographic differences, which reflect an economic base that has increasingly transitioned towards post-industrial urban productive sectors, set the context for the distinct governance challenges faced by rural and urban local governments in Canada in recent years.

For some time now, rural areas in the urban periphery of large cities in Canada have experienced some out-migration of urban residents facing high housing prices in the city. It appears that the Covid-19 pandemic has rapidly intensified this trend, to the extent that may fundamentally change the rural-urban dynamic in the longer run. Of course, it is too early to tell if the trend will be sustained. There is not even reliable data on the scale of the out-migration over the course of the pandemic yet. However, it was notable that *all* the experts and practitioners interviewed for this research noted this out-migration as a major

²¹ Calculated from Statistics Canada Census 2016 data reports.

²² Between 2001 and 2016, the rural Canadian population grew by 5.5%, while the overall national population grew by 16.9%. Even this modest rural growth, however, is largely concentrated near urban areas. See Federation of Canadian Municipalities, ‘Rural Challenges, National Opportunity: Shaping the Future of Rural Canada’ (2019).

²³ All data are calculated from Statistics Canada 2016 census of the population data tables.

development and a source of significant challenge, as well as potential opportunity, for rural areas. Interviewees all agreed that the structural driver of the out-migration is the very high cost of housing in large urban centers, most notably Toronto and Vancouver. With the Covid-19 pandemic entrenching work-at-home possibilities for white collar professionals, and simultaneously enhancing the appeal of low-density rural living, this structural trend has rapidly acquired more force.

Speaking about dynamics in the Toronto area, one policy analyst said: ‘Especially with the last year, housing has just moved out of the [Toronto area] and it's encroaching on a lot of these different communities. People who would have loved to have lived in downtown Toronto, but simply can't afford to are buying homes in Oxford County’ – about 150km from Toronto.²⁴ While the experts interviewed for this project all focused on the Ontario context, media reports suggest similar dynamics surrounding other large urban centres.

This influx of new residents and money brings some benefits to rural areas, such as more budget money for municipalities that rely heavily on property taxes and development fees. As one interviewee noted, ‘from a property tax perspective, from a development perspective, it's pretty significant, (...) you go to some of these places, there's a lot of nice new playgrounds and parks and stuff like that. If you go to Innisfil [a rural community one hour north of Toronto], they built one of the nicest libraries I've ever seen. It's like a monument, incredible. And they're like, “yeah, that's development dollars”’.²⁵

The other side of that same coin, of course, is that housing affordability is quickly becoming a major problem in rural communities that are relatively near to urban centres. ‘This notion that affordability is only an urban issue, it really needs to dissipate’, said one respondent. Those households that cash out of hot urban property markets have been driving up housing prices in rural areas at an unprecedented rate, especially since the beginning the Covid-19 pandemic. One interviewee noted that median house prices went up 40 per cent or more during 2020 in many rural communities that are within a two-hour drive of the Toronto area.²⁶ Another challenge that comes with the influx of what one interviewee called ‘rural gentrifiers’²⁷ is that they tend to want more municipal services in communities that have long provided just the basics, putting upward pressure on property taxes.²⁸

Most respondents also noted that the new urban out-migration is leading to cultural and lifestyle tensions in rural areas that are experiencing high rates of influx. ‘It's gonna be a little bit like it was after the Second World War, when a lot of European immigrants showed up in these communities,’ said one interviewee. ‘They haven't seen that kind of change in a generation in two generations really, and they may have a lot of people coming to town that

²⁴ Interview with local government expert, Rural Ontario Institute (20 July 2021)..

²⁵ Interview with local government expert, York University (10 July 2021)..

²⁶ Interview with local government expert, Guelph University (28 July 2021).

²⁷ *ibid.*

²⁸ Interview with local government expert and consultant, Toronto (13 June 2021).

don't look like them, don't engage in the same economic activities that they're used to, that have different expectations. And they may want to set up cricket pitches, not baseball diamonds'.²⁹ Another respondent noted of the new arrivals from urban areas: 'You know, they need to have a big box store, they want some things from you know from the supermarket and stuff, and [long-time residents] are complaining that all these weird products are showing up in the supermarket right like avocados and (...) gluten-free food'.³⁰

It is far too early to tell how extensive this out-migration to rural areas will ultimately be, and whether it will continue after the Covid-19 pandemic. However, it appears that a significant shift in rural-urban dynamics is underway in the parts of rural Canada that are relatively close to major metropolitan centres, with possibly far-reaching knock-on effects on rural governance issues.

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²⁹ *ibid.*

³⁰ Interview with local government expert, York University (10 July 2021).

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